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**Reassessing Pauline Discipleship as a
Framework for Addressing Youth
Disengagement in Nigerian Pentecostal
Churches: Evidence from Christ Apostolic
Church Oke-Itura District, Ikorodu,
Lagos, Nigeria**

Timilehin Daniel OLABIYI

*Department of Religious and Intercultural Studies,
Lead City University, Ibadan*

olabivit@gmail.com, +2348067221209

<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-9283-9826>

Abstract

Youth disengagement in contemporary Christianity is the process whereby young people drift away from church attendance and activities because they find institutional environments relationally isolated, intellectually shallow, or disconnected from real-world issues. This trend poses a significant challenge to the long-term sustainability of the church. This paper reassesses the Pauline concept of discipleship as a model for addressing youth disengagement within Nigerian Pentecostal churches. The rate at which youths raised in Christian homes abandon active participation in church life has become a major concern globally; the Christ Apostolic Church is not exempt from this challenge, as many young adults have migrated to other denominations. Adopting historical and empirical research methods, this study utilizes oral interviews conducted among pastors, youth executives, and church youths to investigate the causes of youth disengagement and propose actionable solutions. The study is anchored on the Relational Discipleship Theory, which emphasizes spiritual growth through intentional relationships, mentorship, modelling, and interpersonal influence. Findings reveal that relationship gaps,

the strict enforcement of certain doctrinal regulations, and vocational and economic challenges are among the major factors contributing to youth disengagement in the church. This paper argues that Apostle Paul's discipleship model was deeply relational and mentorship-oriented, emphasizing spiritual fathering, guidance, and intentional mentoring. Accordingly, the study recommends that church leaders adopt innovative, relational, and mentorship-based discipleship strategies to minimize youth disengagement rates. Furthermore, it recommends that church authorities intentionally address the spiritual, emotional, vocational, financial, and social needs of the youth to promote commitment, a sense of belonging, and long-term participation in the church.

Keywords: Discipleship, Youth Drop-Out, CAC Oke-Itura, Church, Pauline Concept of Discipleship

Introduction

According to data from Barna Group (2023) the disengagement rate among the youths from church and faith has escalated from 59 percent in 2011 to 64 percent in 2019 in less than a decade. This is pointing to the fact that there is high probability that this would have gone up to around 75 percent this year (2026). This is a sign and a call to the authorities of Christ Apostolic Church (CAC) Nigeria and Overseases to discover a new way of discipleship that will retain her youth which will replace the current less effective youth retaining discipleship. "In tracing the founding, the growth and the expansion of the Church from the 1918 (the beginning of a prayer group which metamorphose to CAC) till this present moment, the roles of youths of the Church cannot be left unnoticed. It should be noted however that there is no society that progress progressively without the young men and women who contribute in one capacity or the other to the all-round social, economic and spiritual well-being of such community of which they are member (Institute of Church and Society, 2021). According to Oniya, the youths are "infused with relentless energy, vigour and drive, that have been found to be the catalyst to positive development in any given society" (Oniya, 2026). It be noted that the Youth ministries and other youth related religious Groups are platform through which religious organization, Government and churches can give back to the youth in their communities and the Nation at large. By definition, the United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) refer to "youth as the period of transition from the dependence of childhood to adulthood independence and awareness of our interdependence as members of a

community” (UNESCO, 2021). According to CAC doctrine and practices put together in her constitution, “the age limit of youth is fifty years. Hence, as Afolabi put it “C.A.C youths are classified as Pre-Teenagers, Teenagers, Real youths, Young Adults and Elderly Youths” (Afolabi, 2023).

The increasing rate of youth drop-out from churches has become a major concern in contemporary Christianity, particularly within Pentecostal and indigenous African churches. Many youths who were conceived, born, and raised in Christian homes gradually disengage from church life as they transition into adulthood. Recent studies have shown that youth disengagement from organized Christianity has continued to rise globally (Barna Group, 2019). This development has negatively affected leadership continuity, discipleship, and the future growth of many churches.

Christ Apostolic Church (CAC) Oke-Itura District, Ikorodu, Lagos, is not exempt from this challenge. Despite the active involvement of youths in evangelism, music ministry, prayer programmes, and church administration, many young people continue to migrate to other denominations or completely withdraw from active participation in church life. Several factors such as strict enforcement of doctrinal regulations, lack of mentorship, weak intergenerational relationships, vocational neglect, emotional challenges, entitlement mentality, and moral struggles have contributed to this problem (Afolabi, 2015).

Scholars have argued that effective youth discipleship must go beyond doctrinal teaching to intentional relational mentorship and spiritual guidance (McGarry, 2019). Apostle Paul’s ministry presents a discipleship model rooted in relationship, mentorship, love, and spiritual fathering (Reeves, 2011). However, many churches have not adequately incorporated these relational dimensions into their discipleship structures. Consequently, many youths feel disconnected, unsupported, and spiritually isolated within the church environment.

Although previous studies have examined youth ministry and church growth, limited scholarly attention has been given to Reassessing Pauline Discipleship concept as a practical framework for addressing Youth Disengagement in Nigerian Pentecostal Churches most especially, Christ Apostolic Church. It is against this backdrop that this study Reassesses the Pauline Discipleship as a Framework for Addressing Youth Disengagement in Nigerian Pentecostal Churches: Evidence from Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Itura District.

The aim of this study is to Reassesses the Pauline Discipleship as a Framework for Addressing Youth Disengagement in Nigerian Pentecostal Churches: Evidence from Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Itura District. Ikorodu, Lagos. CAC Oke – Itura District has ministers who are sound in Prophetic and word ministry with love and passion for the youth to function, grow and development. However, with all these, it was observed that most of the youths raised and cared for by these minsters and the church at large do disengage themselves from the Church and even leave at the later time. Therefore the objectives of this study includes, examining the causes of disengagement of youths from Christ Apostolic Church Oke–Itura District, investigate the biblical and Pauline understanding of discipleship, identify the major principles of Pauline discipleship concept such as mentorship, relationship, and spiritual fathering; examine how the Pauline model of discipleship can address youth disengagement from church life, recommend practical discipleship strategies that can help reduce youth disengagement in Christ Apostolic Church.

The following research questions were addressed in the study. What are the factors responsible for youth disengagement in Christ Apostolic Church Oke–Itura District? What is the biblical and Pauline understanding of discipleship? What are the key principles of Pauline discipleship relevant to youth spiritual formation? How can the Pauline model of discipleship be applied to address youth disengagement in the church? What practical strategies can be adopted to reduce youth drop-out in Christ Apostolic Church Oke–Itura District?

This study is significant in several ways to church leadership, theological scholarship, youth ministry practice, and academic research, particularly within the African ecclesial context. The findings of this study will assist church leaders in Christ Apostolic Church and other denominations to better understand the root causes of youth disengagement from church life. It highlights the importance of relational discipleship, mentorship, and spiritual fathering as essential tools for effective youth retention. The study therefore provides practical guidance for pastors, district leaders, and youth coordinators in restructuring discipleship approaches within the church. The study offers practical insights for youth ministers and church workers on how to engage young people more effectively. By emphasizing the Pauline model of discipleship, it encourages a shift from program-centred youth activities to relational and mentorship-based engagement. This will help

improve emotional connection, spiritual growth, and long-term commitment among youths in the church.

Academically, the study contributes to existing literature on Pauline theology, discipleship studies, and practical theology. It expands scholarly understanding of how Pauline relational discipleship can be contextualized within African Pentecostal and indigenous church settings. It also adds to the discourse on youth ministry from a biblical-theological perspective. The study provides a foundation for further research on youth retention, discipleship models, and church growth strategies in African churches. Future researchers may build on this work by exploring comparative studies across denominations or by expanding the scope to other geographical regions. By addressing the issue of youth drop-out, this study indirectly contributes to the sustainability and future growth of the church. Effective implementation of relational discipleship is expected to enhance youth participation, leadership development, and generational continuity within the church.

Literature Review

Pauline Discipleship

Youth disengagement from church life has become a growing concern within global Christianity and particularly within Pentecostal churches in Nigeria. Several studies have examined the causes of declining youth participation, the role of discipleship in spiritual formation, mentorship patterns within churches, and the significance of relational ministry in sustaining youth commitment. This review therefore examines relevant literature under thematic subheadings corresponding to the major variables of the study: Pauline discipleship, youth disengagement, relational mentorship, spiritual fatherhood, church discipleship structures, and youth retention within Nigerian Pentecostalism.

The concept of Pauline discipleship has attracted scholarly attention due to its relational and transformational character. Unlike institutionalized forms of discipleship that focus primarily on doctrinal instruction, Pauline discipleship integrates mentorship, imitation, spiritual formation, and relational guidance. Reeves (2011) argued that Apostle Paul's discipleship model was fundamentally relational rather than merely instructional. According to Reeves, Paul intentionally nurtured converts through close personal interaction, practical guidance, and moral example. Paul's

instruction in 1 Corinthians 11:1, “Follow my example, as I follow the example of Christ,” demonstrates a discipleship framework rooted in imitation and spiritual modeling. Reeves maintained that Paul viewed discipleship as life-on-life transmission of faith and Christian conduct.

Similarly, Banks (2020) explained that Pauline discipleship involved communal formation where believers grew spiritually through participation in Christian community. Paul’s letters reveal deep emotional investment in the spiritual welfare of converts, particularly Timothy, Titus, and the Thessalonian believers. This relational approach distinguished Pauline ministry from purely formal religious instruction. McGarry (2019) further observed that biblical discipleship in both the Old and New Testaments was intergenerational and relational. According to him, discipleship entails intentional mentoring relationships through which mature believers nurture younger believers toward spiritual maturity. He argued that effective youth ministry must move beyond entertainment-centered activities to intentional spiritual formation.

Furthermore, Longenecker (2016) maintained that Paul’s discipleship theology combined doctrine with ethical transformation. Paul emphasized not only belief systems but also behavioral transformation, communal accountability, and spiritual maturity. This perspective suggests that Pauline discipleship addresses both the spiritual and practical dimensions of Christian living. Within African Pentecostal contexts, Asamoah-Gyadu (2013) argued that discipleship remains central to sustaining church growth and continuity. However, he noted that many Pentecostal churches prioritize charisma, prosperity, and programmes over intentional mentoring structures, thereby weakening long-term spiritual formation among youths. The reviewed literature establishes that Pauline discipleship is relational, mentorship-oriented, and transformational. However, limited studies have specifically examined how Pauline discipleship can practically address youth disengagement within Christ Apostolic Church contexts in Nigeria.

Youth Disengagement from Church Life

Youth disengagement from organized Christianity has become a major concern globally and within African churches. Several scholars attribute this phenomenon to relational disconnect, cultural shifts, identity struggles, and inadequate discipleship structures. Barna Group (2019) reported that youth disengagement from church has continued to rise significantly over

the years. The study revealed that many youths raised in Christian homes gradually disconnect from church communities due to lack of meaningful relationships, unanswered questions, emotional isolation, and perceived irrelevance of church programmes. The report further emphasized that young people who experience intentional mentorship are more likely to remain committed to church life.

Dean (2010) argued that many churches unintentionally promote what she termed “moralistic therapeutic deism,” where Christianity is reduced to moral instruction and personal comfort rather than transformational discipleship. According to her, shallow spirituality contributes significantly to youth disengagement because many young people fail to develop deep personal commitment to Christian faith. Similarly, Smith and Denton (2005) observed that many youths within contemporary Christianity struggle with faith continuity because churches often fail to integrate them into authentic Christian community. Their findings showed that relational belonging strongly influences long-term spiritual commitment among youths. Within the African context, Kalu (2008) noted that rapid social change, urbanization, and globalization have significantly affected youth participation in church life. Nigerian youths increasingly encounter competing ideologies, secular influences, and economic pressures that weaken church commitment. Kalu argued that churches must intentionally develop contextual discipleship structures capable of addressing contemporary youth realities. Afolabi (2015), in his study on youth organizations in Christ Apostolic Church, observed that youths contribute significantly to evangelism, worship, leadership development, and church growth. However, the study identified weak mentorship systems, leadership neglect, and inadequate support structures as major factors affecting youth participation and continuity within the church.

The literature therefore reveals that youth disengagement is often relational and structural rather than merely doctrinal. Nevertheless, insufficient scholarly attention has been given to the role of Pauline relational discipleship in addressing this challenge within indigenous Pentecostal churches such as Christ Apostolic Church.

Relational Mentorship and Spiritual Formation

Relational mentorship is a major component of effective Christian discipleship and youth retention. Scholars consistently emphasize that

spiritual growth occurs most effectively within intentional mentoring relationships. Bandura's (1977) Social Learning Theory explains that individuals learn values, attitudes, and behaviors through observation, imitation, and interaction with role models. This theory has significant implications for Christian discipleship because younger believers often imitate the spiritual lifestyle of mature Christian leaders. Applying this theory to church contexts, Wilkins (1992) argued that discipleship involves relational transmission of Christian identity and practice. According to him, spiritual maturity develops through sustained interaction between mentors and disciples.

Furthermore, Clinton (2012) maintained that mentorship is indispensable for leadership development within the church. Effective mentors provide emotional support, accountability, guidance, and spiritual direction that shape the character and commitment of younger believers. Smith (2016) also emphasized that Christian formation is shaped more by relationships, habits, and communal practices than by intellectual knowledge alone. Spiritual transformation occurs through participation in communities that intentionally nurture Christian identity and belonging. Within African Christianity, Omenyo (2006) noted that communal relationships traditionally play significant roles in spiritual formation. African ecclesiology naturally supports relational discipleship because African societies emphasize communal identity and interdependence. However, modernization and institutionalization have weakened these traditional mentoring patterns in many churches.

The reviewed studies establish that relational mentorship significantly influences youth spiritual formation and retention. However, many churches still operate programme-centered ministries without intentional mentoring systems capable of sustaining youth commitment.

Spiritual Fatherhood in Pauline Ministry

Spiritual fatherhood constitutes another major aspect of Pauline discipleship. Paul frequently described himself as a spiritual father responsible for nurturing believers toward maturity. According to Fee (2011), Paul's relationship with Timothy exemplifies spiritual fatherhood within early Christianity. Paul combined doctrinal teaching with emotional support, correction, encouragement, and practical guidance. This fatherly relationship strengthened Timothy's leadership confidence and spiritual

commitment. Similarly, Wright (2013) argued that Pauline ministry involved pastoral care deeply rooted in affection, sacrifice, and personal investment. Paul's letters consistently reveal emotional attachment to his converts and concern for their spiritual welfare. Adeyemo (2006) observed that spiritual fatherhood resonates strongly within African religious culture because African societies traditionally value elder guidance and communal nurturing. However, many contemporary churches have failed to develop healthy mentoring relationships capable of supporting younger believers emotionally and spiritually.

Furthermore, Stott (1994) explained that spiritual fatherhood within Pauline theology was not authoritarian domination but sacrificial service aimed at producing mature believers. Paul's authority emerged from love, example, and relational commitment rather than institutional control alone. The literature demonstrates that spiritual fatherhood is central to Pauline discipleship and highly relevant to addressing youth disengagement within African church settings.

Discipleship Structures in Nigerian Pentecostal Churches

Several scholars have examined discipleship practices within Nigerian Pentecostalism and indigenous African churches. While Pentecostal churches have experienced remarkable growth, concerns remain regarding the depth and sustainability of discipleship structures. Kalu (2008) argued that African Pentecostalism has achieved rapid expansion largely through revivalism, healing ministries, and charismatic worship. However, many churches struggle with systematic discipleship capable of producing spiritually mature believers. Asamoah-Gyadu (2013) similarly observed that many Pentecostal churches emphasize spiritual experiences and church programmes while neglecting intentional mentoring and long-term spiritual formation. This imbalance contributes to instability among younger members. Within Christ Apostolic Church specifically, Afolabi (2015) noted that youth ministries contribute significantly to church growth through evangelism, music, administration, and prayer activities. Nevertheless, leadership gaps, generational tensions, and weak discipleship structures continue to affect youth retention.

Ojo (2010) further observed that many Nigerian Pentecostal churches struggle to balance doctrinal conservatism with relational engagement. Excessive emphasis on regulations without adequate pastoral sensitivity

sometimes alienates younger members. Additionally, Falaye (2019) argued that contemporary Nigerian youths desire authentic relationships, practical guidance, vocational support, and emotional belonging within church communities. Churches that fail to address these needs often experience increasing youth disengagement.

The literature therefore indicates that while Nigerian Pentecostal churches excel in evangelism and revival activities, many still lack sustainable relational discipleship systems necessary for long-term youth retention.

Empirical Gap in Literature

Existing literature has extensively discussed youth ministry, discipleship, mentorship, church growth, and Pentecostal spirituality. Scholars have also examined Pauline theology and relational discipleship independently. However, there is limited scholarly attention on the application of Pauline discipleship as a practical framework for addressing youth disengagement within Christ Apostolic Church contexts in Nigeria. Most previous studies focus broadly on church growth, youth ministry challenges, or Pentecostal practices without specifically connecting Pauline relational discipleship principles to youth retention strategies in indigenous Pentecostal churches. Furthermore, few studies have empirically examined how mentorship, spiritual fatherhood, and relational engagement within Pauline theology can address youth disengagement in Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Itura District, Ikorodu, Lagos.

This study therefore fills this scholarly gap by reassessing Pauline discipleship as a framework for addressing youth disengagement within Nigerian Pentecostal churches using Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Itura District as a case study.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Relational Discipleship theory which is ministry framework as popularized by leaders like Jim Putman (2010) and Dann Spader (2014) that rejects program-driven church models in favor of intentional, life-on-life small groups modeled after Jesus' method of spiritual multiplication. The theory emphasizes that spiritual formation and discipleship are most effectively achieved through intentional relationships, mentorship, modeling, and interpersonal influence. Relational discipleship goes beyond the mere transmission of doctrinal

knowledge to focus on guidance, accountability, encouragement, and practical Christian living through close interaction between spiritually mature believers and younger converts.

The theory is clearly reflected in the ministry of Apostle Paul. Paul's relationship with Timothy, Titus, and other converts demonstrates a discipleship model rooted in spiritual fatherhood, mentorship, emotional connection, sacrificial love, and practical guidance. His instruction, "Follow my example, as I follow the example of Christ" (New International Version, 2011, 1 Cor. 11:1), reveals a relational approach to spiritual formation. Paul viewed discipleship not merely as teaching doctrines but as nurturing believers through intentional life-on-life relationships (Reeves, 2011). The relevance of this theory to the present study lies in its explanation that many youths disengage from church not simply because of doctrinal disagreements, but due to the absence of meaningful relationships, mentorship, emotional support, and spiritual guidance within the church community.

Relational discipleship therefore provides a framework through which older believers and church leaders intentionally nurture younger believers toward spiritual maturity and active participation in the life of the Church. The study also draws insight from the Social Learning Theory developed by Albert Bandura. According to Bandura (1977), individuals learn behaviours, attitudes, and values through observation, imitation, and interaction with role models. This theory supports the Pauline model of discipleship where younger believers learn Christian conduct and spiritual discipline through close association with spiritually mature leaders. Therefore, the Pauline concept of discipleship provides both a theological and practical framework for addressing youth disengagement within Nigerian Pentecostal churches through mentorship, relational engagement, spiritual fathering, and intentional leadership development.

Methodology

This study is situated within the fields of Church History and Practical Theology. The study adopted both historical and empirical research methods in examining the relational discipleship concept of Pauline discipleship as a model for addressing youth disengagement within Nigerian Pentecostal by paying attention to Christ Apostolic Church Oke–Itura District, Ikorodu, Lagos State. The study area was Christ Apostolic Church Oke–Itura

District, one of the major districts under Christ Apostolic Church Ikorodu DCC, Lagos State, Nigeria. The choice of this District was informed by the increasing concern over the disengagement and migration to other denominations among young adults within the church.

Both primary and secondary sources of data were utilized for this study. Primary data were obtained through oral interviews and personal observations. A total of five respondents—comprising the District Secretary, District Youth Coordinator, Church Minister, Youth Executive, and a Youth Fellowship leader—were purposively selected to serve as key informants. These individuals were chosen based on their strategic knowledge and involvement in youth ministry within the District. This selection criteria prioritized qualitative depth over statistical breadth, ensuring that the data collected reflects the nuanced lived experiences of those most central to the discipleship process (Creswell & Poth, 2018). The interviews provided firsthand information on the causes of youth drop-out, challenges confronting the youths, and possible solutions to the problem. The study also employed participant observation during church programmes and youth fellowship activities within the District to complement the interview data. Secondary data were sourced from relevant published and unpublished materials such as books, journal articles, dissertations, theses, conference papers, dictionaries, encyclopedias, church documents, and internet materials related to discipleship, youth ministry, Pauline theology, and church growth. Various academic libraries and online scholarly databases were consulted for relevant literature. The data collected from both primary and secondary sources were analyzed using descriptive and interpretive methods. Emphasis was placed on Pauline principles of discipleship such as love, mentorship, relationship, and spiritual fathering as practical frameworks for addressing youth disengagement within Nigerian Pentecostal churches using Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Itura District as a case study

Data Presentation and Discussion

Causes of Youth Disengagement in Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Itura District

- 1. Weak Mentorship and Discipleship Structures:*** Findings from interviews revealed that one of the major causes of youth disengagement is the absence of intentional mentorship structures. Pastor Michael

Adebayo noted that while youths actively participate in church programmes, there is limited structured discipleship that connects them personally with spiritual mentors. Similarly, Pastor Samuel Ogunleye observed that church engagement is largely programmatic rather than relational. According to him, “many youths are active in choir, prayer units, and evangelism, but they lack personal spiritual fathers who guide them consistently.” Deaconess Funke Akinloye further emphasized that the absence of mentorship creates emotional and spiritual distance between youths and church leadership, leading to gradual withdrawal from active participation. This finding aligns with McGarry (2019), who emphasized that effective discipleship must be relational and intergenerational rather than program-based. Reeves (2011) similarly argued that Pauline discipleship is rooted in life-on-life mentorship, where spiritual growth is transmitted through close relationships.

2. ***Relational Disconnect Between Church Leaders and Youths:*** Another recurring issue identified is the relational gap between church leadership and youths. Brother Timothy Olabiyi explained that many youths feel uncomfortable approaching church leaders due to perceived authority barriers and fear of criticism. Sister Grace Bamidele added that emotional and social struggles faced by youths are often not adequately addressed within church structures, leading to feelings of isolation. This supports Barna Group’s (2019) observation that youth disengagement often results from lack of meaningful relational connection within church environments. Smith and Denton (2005) also emphasized that belongingness and relational authenticity significantly influence youth retention in faith communities.
3. ***Strict Doctrinal Enforcement and Legalistic Tendencies:*** Respondents also identified strict doctrinal enforcement without adequate relational explanation as a contributing factor to youth disengagement. Pastor Samuel Ogunleye noted that some church practices are implemented in ways that appear rigid to younger members, especially when explanations are not provided. Pastor Michael Adebayo clarified that while doctrinal discipline remains essential, its communication must be pastoral and relational to avoid misunderstanding among youths. Dean (2010) supports this finding by arguing that rigid religious systems without relational grounding often alienate younger generations. Ojo

(2010) similarly noted that excessive legalism can weaken youth commitment in Pentecostal contexts.

4. ***Vocational and Economic Challenges:*** Economic hardship was also identified as a major factor influencing youth disengagement. Deaconess Funke Akinloye explained that many youths struggle to balance church involvement with financial responsibilities and career development challenges. Sister Grace Bamidele noted that the church currently provides limited structured support for vocational training and career advancement. This finding supports Afolabi (2015), who observed that socio-economic factors significantly affect youth participation in Christ Apostolic Church. Kalu (2008) also emphasized that African youths face increasing economic pressures that shape their religious engagement.
5. ***Moral Struggles and Peer Influence:*** Respondents further identified moral and behavioral challenges, including sexual temptation, peer pressure, and social media influence, as factors contributing to youth withdrawal. Brother Timothy Olabiyi noted that many youths struggle privately with moral issues but lack accountability structures within the church. This aligns with Bandura's (1977) Social Learning Theory, which explains that behavior is shaped through observation and environmental influence. Without positive role models, youths may adopt alternative lifestyles outside the church context.

Pauline Discipleship as a Framework for Youth Engagement

1. ***Relational Mentorship in Pauline Model:*** Respondents consistently emphasized that youths require deeper relational engagement rather than programme-based participation alone. Rev. Dr. Michael Adebayo stated that "Pauline discipleship demonstrates that spiritual growth is sustained through mentorship, not just instruction." Pastor Samuel Ogunleye referenced Paul's relationship with Timothy as a model of intentional spiritual fatherhood and guidance. Paul's instruction: 1 Corinthians 11:1 "Follow my example, as I follow the example of Christ" (NIV, 2011), reflects a relational model of discipleship grounded in imitation and mentorship. Reeves (2011) supports this interpretation, noting that Paul's ministry was centered on relational formation rather than institutional teaching alone.
2. ***Spiritual Fatherhood and Emotional Support:*** The study revealed that emotional support is a critical factor in youth retention. Sister Grace

Bamidele observed that many youths desire acceptance, encouragement, and emotional understanding from church leaders. Deaconess Funke Akinloye added that lack of emotional connection often leads to withdrawal from church activities. Wright (2013) argues that Pauline ministry combined doctrinal teaching with deep emotional investment in believers. This reinforces the need for spiritual fatherhood in contemporary discipleship models.

3. ***Vocational Dimension of Pauline Discipleship:*** Respondents also highlighted the need for vocational empowerment within discipleship structures. Pastor Samuel Ogunleye recommended integrating skill acquisition and entrepreneurship training into youth development programs. Rev. Dr. Michael Adebayo noted that Paul's tent-making practice provides a biblical model for integrating faith and work. Hock (1980) explains that Paul's vocational life demonstrated self-reliance and dignity of labor, which supports holistic discipleship that includes economic development.

Proposed Solutions from Respondents

1. ***Structured Mentorship Systems:*** All respondents agreed on the need for structured mentorship programs where mature believers are assigned to guide youths spiritually and morally. This reflects Pauline relational discipleship as emphasized by Reeves (2011).
2. ***Vocational Empowerment Programs:*** The church is encouraged to develop: skills acquisition centers, entrepreneurship training, career mentoring programs. Afolabi (2015) supports this view by linking socio-economic empowerment to increased youth participation in church life.
3. ***Balanced Discipleship Approach:*** Respondents stressed the importance of balancing doctrine with relational engagement. Church teachings should be communicated with pastoral sensitivity rather than rigid enforcement. Dean (2010) similarly warns against moralistic and legalistic approaches that alienate young believers.

Summary of Findings

The findings reveal that youth disengagement in Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Itura District is primarily driven by relational disconnect, inadequate mentorship structures, socio-economic challenges, and insufficient emotional support rather than doctrinal disagreement, and doctrinal

rigidity without pastoral balance. These findings are consistent with existing literature, which emphasizes the importance of relational discipleship in sustaining youth engagement (Barna Group, 2019; McGarry, 2019).

The study further establishes that the Pauline model of discipleship, characterized by mentorship, relational engagement, and spiritual fathering, vocational integration, emotional support, and intentional discipleship structures provides a viable framework for addressing youth disengagement in the church context. Overall, the findings confirm that youth retention is more strongly influenced by relational discipleship than by programme-based church structures alone.

Conclusion

The research revealed that youth disengagement from church life is a growing concern influenced by multiple factors, including weak mentorship structures, relational gaps between leaders and youths, strict doctrinal enforcement without pastoral balance, socio-economic challenges, and moral struggles.

Findings from both interviews and observations indicate that youth disengagement is a response to inadequate relational engagement and insufficient discipleship structures within the church. The study further established that the Pauline model of discipleship is fundamentally relational, emphasizing mentorship, spiritual fathering, love, and personal investment in the lives of believers. In light of the findings, it is evident that the Pauline approach to discipleship provides a relevant and effective framework for addressing youth disengagement in contemporary church settings. When properly implemented, it will foster spiritual growth, emotional stability, moral accountability, and long-term commitment to church life among youths.

Recommendations

It is important now that the researcher make recommendations which will control the rate of Youth disengagement in the Church:

1. The Church needs to reconsider its discipleship methods, adopting relational discipleship concept of Pauline discipleship to address the rate of youth disengagement in the Church.

2. The Church must rediscover Christian calling and Establish Formal structured mentorship system within the church where spiritually mature members are assigned to guide youths in their spiritual, moral, and personal development. This reflects the Pauline model of spiritual fathering and imitation.
3. The Church should promote and encourage ministers called by God into youth Ministry so as to provide Pastoral care, structured counselling services to address emotional struggles, peer pressure, identity issues, and moral challenges affecting youths within the church.
4. The church authority should in their capacity cater for the youth in some neglected aspects such as skills acquisition, career development initiatives, and entrepreneurial training to address the economic challenges faced by youths. This will help them balance faith and livelihood responsibilities.

Implementing these recommendations will not only reduce youth disengagement but also strengthen discipleship culture, promote church growth, and ensure long-term spiritual sustainability within Christ Apostolic Church and similar faith communities.

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